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Cover: graphic reworking of a sheet from Van Dyck's Italian Sketchbook depicting Sofonisba Anguissola

THEORY AND CRITICISM OF LITERATURE AND ARTS

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The date of the meeting between Antoon Van Dyck and Sofonisba Anguissola in Palermo

CARLA ROSSI

On 12 July 1629, Antoon Van Dyck paid a visit to Sofonisba Anguissola in Palermo and recorded the meeting in his Italian notebook, now preserved in the British Museum,⁵ where it is clearly stated (FIG.1): *Ritratto della Signora Sofonisma pittrice, fatto dal vivo in Palermo l'anno 1629, li 12 di Julio: l'età di essa 96.*⁶

FIG. 1

⁵ Under the reference 1957,1214,207,110.

⁶ I transcribe below the original text, freely available online, with the possibility of zooming into the document: *Ritratto della Signora Sofonisma pittrice, fatto dal vivo in Palermo l'anno 1629, li 12 di Julio: l'età di essa 96, havendo ancora la memoria et l'serverllo prontissimo, cortesissima, et sebene per la*

FIG. 2, The date detail in Van Dyck's notebook

It is fascinating to note that the British Museum has a copy of this of this manuscript sheet, made by the British painter and collector Hugh Howard (1675-1738), FIG. 3 and 3bis, a copy that leaves no doubt about the date that appears in Van Dyck's diary, namely 12 July 1629.

The issue with this Van Dyck's manuscript note is that all those who cite it, unfortunately without exception, rather than checking the original document in person, simply rely on an incorrect transcription, attributable (as far as I have reconstructed) to Sir Herbert Cook, in *More Portraits by Sofonisba Anguissola* (1915), and never bother to correct it (to such an extent that the error even appears on the British museum's website).

Cook, who was the owner of Van Dyck's Italian notebook for a certain period of time, read 1624 instead of 1629, and this generated a series of misinterpretations and misunderstandings, that led some critics to claim that Sofonisba, on the occasion of the visit of the young Flemish painter, could no longer remember her own exact age (which would be in clear contrast with what Van Dyck himself said about her *memoria et l' serverllo prontissimo*).

vecc[h]iaia la mancava la vista, hebbe con tutto ciò gusto de mettere gli quadri avanti ad essa et con gran stento mettendo il naso sopra il quadro, venne a discernere qualche poco. Et pigliò gran piacere ancora in quel modo; facendo il ritratto de essa, me diede diversi advertimenti non dovendo pigliar il lume troppo alto, acciò che le ombre nelle rughe della vecc[h]iaia non diventassero troppo grandi, et molti altri buoni discorsi, come ancora contò parte della vita di essa per la quale si conobbe che era pittrice de natura et miracolata et la pena maggiore che hebbe era per mancamento di vista non poter più dipingere: la mano era ancora ferma senza tremula nessuna. Although I announced this article a few months ago in the Italian magazine *Aboutart*, I find myself obliged here, for reasons of space, to refer to a broader study that will be included in a forthcoming booklet. I anticipate here, therefore, the crux of the matter, raising more questions than giving certainties.

FIG. 3, https://www.britishmuseum.org/collection/object/P_1874-0808-23

Drawn by Hugh Howard, after Anthony van Dyck, Portrait of Sofonisba Anguissola, from Van Dyck's sketch of her at the age of 96

FIG. 3bis

An additional piece of information provided by Van Dyck concerns the painter's age in 1629, i.e. 96 years, which means that she was born in 1532.

Although the Diocesan Archive in Cremona does not seem to have any records that would help to settle the question of the painter's exact date of birth, we owe to Anguissola's second husband, Orazio Lomellini, a Genoese consul in Palermo, an epigraph engraved on a commemorative plaque in the now deconsecrated church of San Giorgio dei Genovesi, placed there in 1632 (not by chance opposite the chapel of San Luca), on the occasion of the centenary of the painter's birth.

This is the text that can still be clearly read today: Sophonisbae uxori ab Anguissolae – comitibus ducenti origine(m) parentu(m) – nobilitate, forma extraordinariisque – naturae dotibus in illustres mundi mulieres – relatae, ac in exprimendis hominum – imaginibus adeo insigni – ut pare(m) aetatis suae – nemine(m) habuisse sit aestimata – Horatius Lomellinus – ingenti affectus maerore decus – hoc extremum et si tantae mulieri exiguum – mortalibus vero maximu(m) dicavit 1632.

The memorial plaque thus seems to confirm Van Dyck's indication that Sofonisba was 96 years old in 1629.

In the *Liber Mortuorum* of the parish of Santa Croce in Palermo (ASDPa, Archivio Storico Parrocchia Santa Croce, no. 3772, c. 3) the following death certificate is transcribed (FIG. 4): *fu sep[ol]ta nella chiesa di S. Giorgio delli Genovisi la sign[or]a Sifonisma Lo Millino.*

FIG. 4, ASDPa, Archivio Storico Parrocchia Santa Croce, no. 3772, c. 3

How is it possible that Van Dyck met Sofonisba alive and in good health on 12 July 1629? Is it to be assumed that Van Dyck wrote an incorrect date in his notebook and consequently that Sofonisba, due to her old age, could no longer remember her own date of birth and told Van Dyck that she was 96 instead of 92? Why is there no grave under the polychrome marble slab with the Latin epigraph, commissioned in 1632 by Sofonisba's second husband, Orazio Lomellini,⁷ in the right aisle of the Church of San Giorgio dei Genovesi? And again, if the painter had really been buried on 16 November 1625 in the Church of San Giorgio, built between 1575 and 1596 in the outermost part of the Loggia district, what reason did Lomellini have, only seven years after the presumed death of his beloved wife, to put up the memorial slab in her memory, instead of having a mass sung for her soul, as was the custom at the time?

The answer to all these questions is perhaps quite trivial: Sofonisba had no children, but maintained cordial contacts with her distant nephews in Cremona (the sources mention that a daughter of Europa Anguissola, Bianca, maintained correspondence with her aunt) and especially with Giulio, the natural son of Orazio Lomellini, who appears in various guises in numerous acts of his stepmother, in whose honour he had his only daughter baptised with the name Sofonisma (the name appears with the usual alternation of the sound bilabial occlusive -b- with the sound bilabial nasal -m-).

⁷ Orazio Lomellini was Sofonisba's second husband, married in Pisa in 1579. Orazio was consul of the Genoese nation in Palermo from 1615, having previously been a prominent member of the Ligurian community in Sicily.

At the State Archive of Palermo is preserved, among others, a notarial document signed by Giulio Lomellini, dated 31 January 1624 (a year before the registration of the burial), which reads as follows:⁸

quam [...] pater et legitimus administrator Hettoris, Horatii, Julii Cesaris et Sofonisme Lomellino, eius filiorum.

Giulio Lomellini, as all genealogies of Genoese patrician families report,⁹ had four children: Hector, Horace, Julius Caesar and Sophonisba, who were born in the early seventeenth century.

The record of the burial in the Church of San Giorgio dei Genovesi, on 16 November 1625, may therefore refer to the young Signora Sofonisba Lomellini, Giulio's daughter, not to the painter herself. The death, in '25, of Giulio's daughter, is also reported in the *Libro di Secretia* of Palermo.

Finally, it should be noted that the painter herself appears in notarial documents as *Sofonisba Lomelina et Anguissola*, a name with which she also signed official letters, including one dated 14 October 1583 sent to Philip II of Spain, preserved in the Archivio General de Simancas, Valladolid (FIG. 5).

A photograph of a handwritten signature in dark ink on aged, light brown paper. The signature is written in a cursive script and reads: "humilissima sua et fidelissima Vasalla Sofonisba Lomelina et Anguissola". The text is arranged in four lines, with the first two lines being smaller and more decorative, and the last two lines being larger and more legible.

FIG. 5

⁸ ASPa, Notai defunti, stanza I, Francesco Comito 922, c. 363, 31 gennaio 1624.

⁹ Papers of the Lomellini family can be found in the Pallavicino Archive included in the Durazzo Giustiniani private archival complex in Genoa, while the reference parish archives are: Genoa, Parish of Sant'Agnesse and Nostra Signoria del Carmine; Parish of San Siro; Parish of San Pietro in Banchi.